

DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITIES OF THE INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES IN THE PREVENTION OF CRIMES DURING PUBLIC EVENTS

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Annotation

The article focuses on the importance of holding public events in the public order maintenance activities of internal affairs bodies. In this regard, it is aimed at determining the role of internal affairs bodies in ensuring public safety, the directions for improving their activities.

It is an effective tool for the prevention of crimes, quick detection and detection of violations, preventive effect and coordination of the activities of law enforcement agencies in public order maintenance activities of internal affairs bodies. At the same time, it is described that the legal basis and integration mechanisms will be organized based on modern requirements.

Keywords. public order, public safety, prevention, public events.

1. Introduction

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan proclaimed the establishment of a democratic state governed by the rule of law in our country. In building a democratic state governed by the rule of law, the activities of law enforcement agencies—prosecutor's offices, justice, internal affairs, and others—occupy a leading position in the implementation and strengthening of legality and law and order.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan imposes on the state the obligation to protect one of the most fundamental tasks—the rights and freedoms of man and citizen. Internal affairs bodies play a significant role in fulfilling this obligation. Among the many factors determining the effectiveness of internal affairs bodies in ensuring the security of the individual and society, protecting public order, and protecting the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, the management and organization of labor are also important in the implementation of other tasks assigned to them.

Internal affairs bodies occupy a leading position in the system of law enforcement agencies of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its bodies are state law enforcement agencies that protect citizens, their rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, as well as the interests of society and the state, from various illegal encroachments.

The role of law enforcement agencies in the system of state bodies is determined by the fact that they were created to perform the state's law enforcement function. Law enforcement agencies perform the functions of protecting state law and order, protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens, and combating offenses and crime. This function, by its essence and content, serves the establishment of justice, humanism, the strengthening of legislation, and the formation of a rule-of-law state and culture.

The role and place of crime prevention in the fundamental reforms being carried out in the judicial and legal sphere of our country, particularly in the policy of combating crime, are

significantly increasing. Over the past period, a completely new system for crime prevention and the fight against crime has been created that meets modern requirements. The most urgent task has become the early prevention of illegal acts, rather than merely fighting the consequences of offenses under the threat of punishment."

The creation of an effective system for the early prevention of offenses in our country, increasing legal culture in society, instilling in citizens a respect for the law and an intolerant attitude toward any form of violation of the law, coordinating preventive work, and implementing modern organizational and legal mechanisms for the general prevention of offenses are relevant. It is also important to study the prospects for improving the system of eliminating the causes and conditions for the commission of offenses.

Over the past period, comprehensive measures for the prevention of offenses have been implemented in the republic, and a unified regulatory and legal framework has been formed to regulate social relations in this field. As a result of the effective operation of the crime prevention system, law and order have been strengthened in the country, and the criminogenic situation has significantly improved.

It is well known that in ensuring public order in society, rules of conduct and norms based on ensuring public peace and proper behavior are of great importance. Relations in this field in the Republic of Uzbekistan are regulated by laws and bylaws, as well as moral norms, customs, and traditions, and provide for liability for any unlawful acts aimed at encroaching on relations in the field of ensuring public order. In particular, the Criminal[2] and Administrative Responsibility Codes of the Republic of Uzbekistan[3] establish liability for acts against public order.

It should be noted that one of the unlawful acts encroaching on relations in the field of ensuring public order is the crime of hooliganism. Although a number of regulatory documents aimed at maintaining public order and ensuring the safety of citizens have been adopted in our country over the past period, the scientific and practical study of the causes and conditions associated with the commission of hooliganism is of great importance in the early prevention of this crime.

2. Materials and Methods:

Improving the management and organization of the activities of internal affairs bodies is a necessary factor in improving the work of this body and, ultimately, ensuring the protection of the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens. Under modern conditions, knowledge of the scientific foundations of management and the organization of labor for employees of internal affairs bodies is extremely important for the effective performance of their managers and specialists.

It is well known that ensuring public order and safety is universally recognized as one of the primary functions of the state. Various organizational and legal mechanisms are developed and implemented to implement this function. In particular, the holding of thousands of mass political, cultural, and sports events annually in our republic testifies to the reign of tranquility and peace in our country.

Currently, in accordance with the regulatory legal document approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 205 dated July 29, 2014, "On measures to further improve the procedure for organizing and holding mass events," the concept of a "mass event" is defined as follows: "A mass event is recognized as a gathering of

people organized by legal entities and individuals in open and closed structures, squares, buildings, and other places for the purpose of conducting entertainment, theatrical-spectacular, concert, sports, advertising programs, and other leisure programs, as well as national, religious, and professional holidays with the participation of at least 100 people."

In ensuring public order in society, rules of conduct and norms based on ensuring public peace and proper behavior are of great importance. Relations in this field in the Republic of Uzbekistan are regulated by laws and bylaws, as well as moral norms, customs, and traditions, and provide for liability for any unlawful acts aimed at encroaching on relations in the field of ensuring public order. Specifically, the Criminal Code[5] and the Code of Administrative Responsibility[6] of the Republic of Uzbekistan establish liability for acts against public order.

It should be noted that when analyzing the essence of the concepts of "public order" and "public safety," although they differ from each other, their provision shows that they are interconnected and complement each other, and it is very difficult to separate one from the other. Maintaining public order simultaneously encompasses the concepts of ensuring the personal safety of citizens and public safety. However, although the concepts of "personal safety of citizens" and "public safety" are related to the concept of "public order," they differ from each other.

3. Results: (Research results).

In our opinion, the definition of a mass event in ensuring public order in mass events today is understood as a process covering events organized for the purpose of holding socio-political, cultural-mass, and entertainment programs, as well as national religious and professional holidays, with the participation of one or more people at open and closed facilities and structures.

Based on this, it can be concluded that ensuring public order and safety includes law and order, public order, as well as fire safety and road safety.

In our view, public safety is a state of protection of the vital interests of the individual, society, and the state from the consequences of criminal and other unlawful actions, social conflicts, natural disasters, earthquakes, epidemics, epizootics, major catastrophes, accidents, and fires. Therefore, it is very important to consider it from various perspectives, including the definition of the object of control and the methods of influence.

Today, the changes taking place in the socio-political life of our state, especially the tasks related to the security and stability of our country, require a very serious approach, and the systematic, specific, and lawful actions of the internal affairs bodies, as well as their constant improvement, are among the issues awaiting resolution.

A threat to public order and public safety arises due to the violation of the established procedure for holding mass events, the lack of preparation of the venue for them, and the untimely adoption of measures to regulate the movement of large groups of people. In particular, the lack of proper equipment for sports facilities leads to serious consequences.

It should be noted that despite the widespread use of these concepts in our country's legislation and within legal science, a unified approach to their definition has not yet been developed in legal literature [7]. Such an approach requires revealing the essence of concepts such as "public event," "public order," and "public safety" and forming their theoretical definitions.

Approximately 20,000 mass, political, cultural, national, professional, and sports events are held annually in our republic. In turn, more than 90 million participants are participating in these events. Article 200 (Violation of the rules for holding mass events) was introduced into Chapter XV of the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility by the Law on Amendments and Additions to the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility dated April 25, 2003.

The administrative legal norm in this article is mainly applied to the organizers of mass events in the event of non-compliance with the rules for holding mass events, that is, the requirements of the rules "On measures to further improve the procedure for organizing and holding mass events," approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 29, 2014 No. 205.

Factors affecting the maintenance of public order and safety during mass events include:

- public events require the participation of people (the public) (as an active or spectator);
- mainly organized mass movements with defined goals, carried out on the initiative of specific subjects;
- the number of participants will be indefinite;
- held in public places;
- authorization must be obtained in the prescribed manner.

In the practical activities of the internal affairs bodies, offenses encroaching on public order and security are frequently encountered, primarily during mass events. These offenses are considered more socially dangerous than petty hooliganism (Article 183). This is because an offensive act committed during a mass event can lead to mass riots or injuries to many citizens. Currently, in practice, offenses of this nature are qualified by internal affairs bodies as petty hooliganism.

According to the legal scholar Kh.R. Alimov, public order is a system of social relations regulated by moral and legal norms, as well as rules of morality, etiquette, and customs. Public order is protected by state bodies, public associations, and citizens. The main task in this work is performed by the internal affairs bodies.

Another problematic situation arising during mass events in administrative legislation is that Article 202 of the current Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes administrative liability for citizens and officials who create conditions for holding unauthorized meetings, rallies, street processions, and demonstrations, or provide premises or other property (communication means, reproductive and other technical equipment, transport) to their organizers and participants, or create other conditions for such events.

According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 29, 2014, No. 205 "On measures to further improve the procedure for organizing and conducting mass events," state authorities and administration bodies, as well as legal entities and individuals, may be organizers of mass events. Mass events are held in specially designated locations for these purposes, determined by the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the khokimiyats of the regions and the city of Tashkent, after obtaining a corresponding permit. Obtaining a permit for mass events organized in accordance with the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan is not required.

To consider issues regarding the issuance of permits for mass events and to exercise control over them, commissions for monitoring the conduct of mass events are established under the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and the khokimiyats of regions, the city of Tashkent, and districts (cities). The commissions include representatives of the territorial bodies of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the State Security Service, the National Guard, the Ministry of Emergency Situations, the Ministry of Health, and other interested institutions and organizations.

Today, large-scale and systemic reforms have been carried out in our country in the field of law enforcement, especially in the system of internal affairs bodies, which is an important part of it. Initially, these reforms, initiated in the capital of our country by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Concept of Maintaining Public Order and Ensuring Security in the City of Tashkent" dated April 12, 1999, ensured a significant decrease in the crime rate and the improvement of the criminogenic situation in Tashkent, and were subsequently continued throughout the republic in accordance with the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on improving the activities of internal affairs bodies and government decisions adopted to ensure their implementation[10].

As a result of the reforms carried out over the past years to improve the activities of internal affairs bodies, including their focus on maintaining public order and ensuring security, the activities of all sectoral services of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their local subordinate structures have been improved in accordance with modern requirements, and their organizational structure and main tasks have been clearly defined. Additionally, the activities of internal affairs bodies, specifically the patrol and post service units, have been improved to maintain public order and ensure safety during mass events, and the responsibility of their employees has been increased. Along with all sectoral services of the internal affairs bodies, the system of the patrol-post and public order service has been improved, which is directly engaged in maintaining public order and ensuring security.

The material and technical base of sectoral services, structural units, and line units, the primary task of which is the maintenance of public order and ensuring security within the internal affairs system, has been improved, equipped with modern motor vehicles, computer and communication tools, and service weapons; finally, the activities of internal affairs bodies, particularly regarding the maintenance of public order and ensuring security, are being legally strengthened[11].

As a system of social relations that arise and develop in public places on the basis of legal and social norms aimed at maintaining public order, public safety, the normal functioning of organizations, creating full conditions for labor and recreation of citizens, respecting their honor, dignity and general moral values, it is regulated by many imperative norms that must be followed by subjects of law. These norms of an imperative nature are also important in the system of administrative-legal norms, which, firstly, establish mandatory rules related to public order, secondly, are manifested in the functions, powers and rights of the relevant subjects of executive power to maintain public order, and thirdly, determine measures of administrative liability for violation of public order.

In our view, the analysis of the aforementioned problems confirms the need to develop and adopt a draft law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Mass Events," as well as to introduce amendments to a number of laws related to ensuring public safety during other mass events.

Conclusions:

The study confirms that the analysis of the aforementioned problems in public order protection activities currently requires the development and adoption of the draft law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Mass Events," as well as amendments to a number of laws related to ensuring public safety during other mass events

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